

Pronominal Anaphora Processing

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Abstract—Discourse pronominal anaphora resolution must be part of any efficient information processing systems, since the reference of a pronoun is dependent on an antecedent located in the discourse. Contrary to knowledge-poor approaches, this paper shows that syntax-semantic relations are basic in pronominal anaphora resolution. The identification of quantified expressions to which pronouns can be anaphorically related provides further evidence that pronominal anaphora is based on domains of interpretation where asymmetric agreement holds.

Keywords—asymmetric agreement, pronominal anaphora, quantifiers and indefinite expressions.

I. THE PROBLEM

A pronoun lacks independent reference. Proper names and definite descriptions are possible referents to pronouns. This is also the case for indefinite expressions and quantifiers under certain conditions. This paper focuses on cases where a pronoun is anaphorically related to a quantifier in a precedent sentence. In (1), the existential quantifier can be the antecedent of a pronoun. In (2), the universal quantifier cannot be anaphorically related to the individual pronoun *he*, whereas this is possible in (3), where an indefinite expression, *a corporate number*, can be reconstructed as a restrictor for the proposition including the pronoun. This phenomenon is referred to in terms of telescoping in [30].

- (1) *Someone* came to the meeting. *He* was expected to vote on the motion.
- (2) *Everyone* came to the meeting. *He* was expected to vote on the motion.
- (3) *Everyone with a corporate number* came to the meeting. *He* was expected to vote on the motion.

Information processing systems, including information extraction and question answering, must be able to identify the possible antecedents of pronouns, since the information requested in a query or in a question can be traced through discourse pronominal anaphora. For example, the answer to

the question in (4) can be accessed through the linking of the pronoun *he* in the second sentence in (3) to the quantifier phrase *everyone with a corporate number* in the preceding sentence.

- (4) Who voted on the motion?

So-called “knowledge-poor” systems for discourse pronominal anaphora resolution systems [21], [25] use limited linguistic knowledge to identify the antecedents of pronouns. They rely on the string-linear position of pronouns and possible antecedents, without taking into account the fine-grained syntax-semantic properties of the expressions they are part. Consequently, their success rate is poor. For example, Mitkov Anaphora Resolution System (MARS) [27] incorrectly identifies the constituent *the meeting*, instead of the constituent *everybody with a corporate number*, as being the antecedent of the pronoun *he* in the examples (1)-(3) above:

- (5) MARS result for (3): **He** appears in paragraph 2, sentence 2, from position 1 to position 1. It is singular. The antecedent is indicated to be **the meeting** in paragraph 2, sentence 1, from position 7 to position 8.
- (6) MARS result for (2): **He** appears in paragraph 1, sentence 2, from position 1 to position 1. It is singular. The antecedent is indicated to be **the meeting** in paragraph 1, sentence 1, from position 3 to position 4.
- (7) MARS result for (1): **He** appears in paragraph 3, sentence 2, from position 1 to position 1. It is singular. The antecedent is indicated to be **meeting** in paragraph 3, sentence 1, from position 1 to position 1.

The efficiency of information processing systems depends on their ability to process fine-grained syntax-semantic properties of linguistic expressions. What are the syntax-semantic properties of quantifiers and indefinites that make them possible antecedents for pronouns?

Contrary to proper names and definite descriptions, quantifiers and indefinites are usually considered to be non-referential expressions, i.e., they do not refer to individuals in the universe of interpretation.¹ However, a quantified

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¹ A quantifier requires generalizing over the individual entities of the universe of interpretation. For example, the truth of a quantificational statement such as *everyone wrote a program* requires that, for all the individuals in the universe that can be substitutes for x in “x wrote a program”, the outcome is true. The truth of a quantificational statement such as *someone wrote a program* requires finding some individual or other in the universe that can be

expression can be the antecedent of a pronoun, as illustrated above.

The properties of discourse pronominal anaphora have been widely discussed in semantic theory [15], [8], [20], [23], and different approaches to this phenomenon are available in the literature. For example, in the variable binding approach [17], [18], [2], [3], indefinite expressions and quantificational expressions are essentially of the same type. The binding effects observed in examples such as (1) and (3) fall out of an extension of the scope domain of the quantifier. However, the universal quantifier is usually static (but it also has dynamic definitions), which accounts for the lack of binding effect in (2). In the restrictor reconstruction approach [30], telescoping is viewed as the reconstruction of the restrictor of a sentence. In this approach, it is the discourse, including the syntactic properties of the linguistic expressions, that makes it clear that a given sentence is interpreted relative to a restrictor. In fact, the variable binding and the restrictor reconstruction approaches have in common that quantifiers and anaphoric pronouns are asymmetrically related, and that must also be semantically related.

I have shown in [11] that a definite description can be a possible antecedent of a pronoun if it asymmetrically agrees with that pronoun. I focus here on cases where a pronoun is anaphorically related to a quantifier or an indefinite, in order to show that asymmetric agreement is also at play.

The organization of this paper is the following. First, I define the notion of asymmetric relation. Second, I illustrate that pronouns can be bound in different domains. Third, I show how discourse pronominal anaphora resolution based on asymmetric agreement makes correct predictions for the processing of pronouns bound by quantifiers and indefinites.

II. ASYMMETRY THEORY

In Set Theory [32], asymmetry is a property of a relation R such that there are no ordered pairs in R whose members are inverted. Symmetric relations do not have this property.² In linguistic theory [5], [22] the structure of linguistic expressions is represented in terms of oriented graphs, where asymmetric relations are defined in terms of precede, dominate, and asymmetric c -command. Asymmetric c -command (8) is relevant across the board in grammar, including in binding and movement [6], [7], [10], [12], [19], [22], [27], [19], [28]. Thus in (9), X asymmetrically c -commands Y .

- (8) a. *C-command*: X c -commands Y iff X and Y are categories and X excludes Y , and every category that dominates X dominates Y . [22]

substituted for x in "x wrote a program" to interpret the statement *someone wrote a program* as true.

² If $R \subseteq A \times A$, then R is symmetric
 iff $(\forall x y) (\langle x, y \rangle \in R \rightarrow \langle y, x \rangle \in R)$.
 If $R \subseteq A \times A$, then R is asymmetric
 iff $(\forall x y) (\langle x, y \rangle \in R \rightarrow \langle y, x \rangle \notin R)$.

- b. *Asymmetric c-command*: X asymmetrically c -commands Y , if X c -commands Y and Y does not c -command X . [22]

In Asymmetry Theory [10], [12], asymmetric relations are part of morphological and syntactic expressions. The theory correctly predicts that a change in morphological relations gives rise to either gibberish or a difference in semantic interpretation. It also correctly predicts that a change in the syntactic relations brings about a change in information structure. In this theory, the operations of the grammar apply under asymmetric Agree (10), (11). Thus, the features of two related elements are in a proper subset relation.³

- (10) a. Shift (α, β)
 Given two objects α, β , Shift (α, β) derives a new object δ projected from α .
- b. Link (α, β)
 Given two objects α and β , Link (α, β) creates a new object where α and β are featurally related.
- (11) Agree (φ_1, φ_2)
 Given two sets of features φ_1 and φ_2 , Agree (φ_1, φ_2) applies if and only if φ_1 properly includes φ_2 .

In this theory, only elements in asymmetric relation are optimally interpretable at the interfaces with the external systems, conceptual-intentional and sensorimotor.

Asymmetry Theory has implications for natural language technologies, including information extraction and question answering, as shown in [13], [14]. The processing of the asymmetric properties of linguistic expressions is expected to improve any area where human users can benefit by communicating with their computers in a natural way.

III. LOCAL DOMAINS OF INTERPRETATION

Locality is another salient property of natural languages. It has been shown that the syntactic operations apply to local domains and that semantic interpretation is domain-dependent. More recently, the notion of local domain has been thought of in terms of the notion of phase [5], [6], [31]. A syntactic phase is a unit of the computation and interpretation: it has an internal structure, it is subject to impenetrability, and it is isolatable at the interfaces.

³ Given two sets A and B , if all the members of A are also the members of B , A is a subset of B .
 A is a proper subset of B , or is properly included in B , whenever A is a subset of B but A is not equal to B .

A. Morphological Domain

In Asymmetry Theory, local domains of interpretation are also part of the derivation of morphological expressions, such as reflexive pronouns and quantifiers [9], [12]. A morphological domain typically includes two layers: an affix occupies the higher layer, and a root heads the lower layer, as in (12) where α , β , and δ are placeholders for morphological features. A morphological domain is derived by the operations of the grammar applying under asymmetric Agree.

$$(12) [X \ \alpha \ X \ [Y \ \beta \ Y \ \delta]]$$

The configuration in (16) is the minimal domain form for interpretable morphological expressions. Considering quantifiers, operator-variable-restrictor linking applies in their morphological domain. For example, in (13a) *every* is the operator that locally links, under asymmetric Agree, a variable X , and *one* is the local restrictor of X . In syntax, quantifier raising [26], [16] recovers the syntactic operator-variable relation, as illustrated in (14). Considering reflexive pronouns, linking also applies in their morphological domains. The pronoun *him* is a restrictor of the reflexive operator, and it is anaphorically linked to the reflexive head *self* which projects its features to the whole reflexive construct (13b)). Consequently, *himself* is a reflexive pronoun that must be bound by an antecedent in the syntactic domain.

- (14) a. Everybody trusts somebody.
- b. [Everybody [somebody [everybody trusts somebody] $\forall > \exists$ (QR: wide scope universal quantifier)]
- c. [Somebody [everybody [everybody trusts somebody] $\exists > \forall$ (QR: wide scope existential quantifier)]

B. Syntactic Domain

The examples in (15) and (16) illustrate that in the syntactic domain, e.g., in a proposition, a reflexive pronominal, such as *himself*, must be linked to an antecedent, whereas a pronoun, such as *him*, must be free.

(15) [Everyone [trusts himself]].

(16) [Everyone [trusts him]].

The Binding Theory (17), [4], [5] expresses this generalization in terms of two conditions that hold locally in a Binding Domain (BD). If two arguments are bound, they have the same reference. They do not have the same reference if they are free. The notions of 'bound' and 'free' are defined in terms of the asymmetric c-command relation, (18).

- (17) Binding Theory
 A. An anaphor is bound in its BD.
 B. A pronominal is free in its BD.
- (18) α is bound by β iff α and β are co-indexed and β asymmetrically c-commands α
 α is free iff α is not bound.

Asymmetric c-command is a necessary condition for binding. A reflexive anaphor, such as *himself*, must be asymmetrically c-commanded by its local antecedent. A pronoun, such as *him*, must be free in its BD under asymmetric c-command, however, it may be bound by an antecedent that does not asymmetrically c-command it, as illustrated in (19), and (20), where TP stands for Tense Phrase, QP stands for Quantifier Phrase, DP stands for Determiner Phrase, and VP stands for Verb Phrase).

(19) [Everyone who owns a corporate number [uses it]].

Moreover the syntax-semantic properties of the antecedent of a pronoun are also at play, as the following example illustrates.

(21) Everybody with a corporate number thinks that he will vote.

In (21), the antecedent of the pronoun *he* is the full QP constituent *everybody with a corporate number*, see (22) where PP stands for Prepositional Phrase, and CP for Complementizer Phrase).

along with the animate ([±ani]) feature, the part-whole ([±w]) feature, and the group ([±gr]) feature. The [±ani] feature differentiates *he* from *it*, and the [±w] feature, differentiates anaphoric pronouns, such as *himself*, from non-anaphoric pronouns, such as *he* and *him*, and from DPs. Non-anaphoric pronouns and DPs are [+w], anaphoric pronouns are [-w]. The [±gr] feature differentiates QPs with a group reading, such as *everyone*, from those that do not, such as *someone*.

(29) DPros, QP, and DPs formal and semantic features

	Form: pers, num, gen	Sem: Ir, ani, w, gr
DPro	+ + +	- +/- +/- +/-
QP	3 rd pers + u	+ +/- - +/-
DP	3 rd pers + +	+ +/- +/- +/-

V. PREDICTIONS

Pronominal anaphora resolution based on (28) and (29) makes correct predictions. A reflexive pronoun is bound and a pronominal is free under asymmetric c-command in their BD. The features of the antecedent are a superset of the features of the anaphor (see (30), (31)) where the antecedent is a quantifier.

(30) [*Everyone* _z [trusts _m *himself*]]
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, -gr } { -Ir, +ani, -w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }

(31) [*Everyone* _z [trusts = _m *him*]]
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, -gr } { -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }

The BD for pronouns and anaphors is limited to the embedded propositions in the examples in (32) and (33), and within these propositional domains, the reflexive pronoun is bound and the pronominal is free. In (32), *everyone* is the antecedent of *himself*, the features of the antecedent is the superset of the features of the anaphor *himself*. In (33), *everyone*, which is located outside of the binding domain of the pronoun *him*, is a possible antecedent, as the dotted line indicates, for the pronoun *him*. The linking relation is also obtained under asymmetric Agree.

(32) [Someone thinks [that *everyone* trusts _m *himself*]].
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, +gr } { -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }

(33) [*Everyone* thinks [that the president trusts *him*]].

zm
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, -gr } { -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }

In the example in (19) repeated here in (34), the indefinite DP *a corporate number* is the closest possible antecedent for the pronoun *it*, since it does not asymmetrically c-command the pronoun within its BD, but nevertheless enters into an asymmetric Agree relation with it. The set of features of the indefinite DP is a superset of the set of features of the pronoun.

(34) [Everyone who owns [*a corporate number*]
 { +Ir, -ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }
 [uses *it*] g
 zm
 { -Ir, -ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }

Asymmetric Agree is also at play in the domain of the discourse, given (28). The examples in (35) and (36), where the antecedent of the pronoun is a quantifier, illustrate this point.

(35) [[*Someone* came to the meeting]. [*He* was expected to
 zm
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, -gr } { -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, +sing, +masc }
 vote on the motion]].

(36) [[*Everyone* came to the meeting]. [*They* were expected to
 zm
 { +Ir, +ani, +w, +gr } { -Ir, +ani, +w, +gr }
 { +3rdpers, +sing, +u } { +3rdpers, -sing, +masc }
 vote on the motion]].

The proposed system, based on asymmetric Agree, is flexible enough to account for the fact that *everyone* can be the antecedent of a plural pronoun, such as *they* in (36), even though its set of formal features includes +sing. The set of features of *everyone* is the superset of the features of the plural pronoun *they*. Moreover, the system can also handle cases where *everyone* is a possible antecedent for the singular pronoun *he* (37). The difference between *someone* and *everyone* takes the form of a difference in the value of the semantic feature ±gr. *Someone* is -gr, and can only be a possible antecedent for a +sing pronoun, whereas *everyone* is +gr and, in the context of an indefinite expression, such as *with a corporate number*, can be an antecedent for a +sing pronoun (38). In both cases, the quantifier is in asymmetric agreement relation with the pronoun.

(37) [[*Someone* with a corporate number] came to the
 g

{+Ir, +ani, +w, -gr}
 {+3rdpers, +sing, +u}
 meeting]. [[He] was expected to vote on the motion]].
 $\overset{g}{\{ -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr \}}$
 $\{+3^{\text{rd}}\text{pers, +sing, +masc} \}$

(38) [[Everyone with a corporate number] came to the
 $\overset{g}{\{ +Ir, +ani, +w, +gr \}}$
 $\{+3^{\text{rd}}\text{pers, +sing, +u}\}$
 meeting]. [He was expected to vote on the motion]].
 $\overset{g}{\{ -Ir, +ani, +w, -gr \}}$
 $\{+3^{\text{rd}}\text{pers, +sing, +masc} \}$

Asymmetric Agree holds in all the domains of interpretation.

VI. SUMMARY

Knowledge-poor systems for pronominal anaphora resolution cannot handle cases where a quantifier is anaphorically related to a pronoun. The syntax-semantic properties of quantified expressions, indefinites, and pronouns cannot be dealt with by systems that mainly process string-linear properties of linguistic expressions. Knowledge-rich systems are necessary for efficient (bound) pronominal anaphora resolution. DD-Linking is a syntax-semantic discourse interface condition requiring that a pronoun, i.e., an element that lacks independent reference, be linked to an antecedent with which it asymmetrically agrees. Linking applies to domains of interpretation, which may in some cases reconstruct for the interpretation of pronouns related to quantifiers. Pronominal anaphora resolution crucially relies on the dynamic syntax-semantic processing of these domains.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Carter, *Interpreting Anaphora in Natural Language Texts*, Chichester: Ellis Horwood, 1987.
- [2] G. Chierchia, "Anaphora and dynamic binding," *Linguistics and Philosophy*, vol. 15, pp. 111-183, 1992.
- [3] G. Chierchia, *Dynamics of Meaning*. Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1995.
- [4] N. Chomsky, *Lectures on Government and Binding*, Dordrecht: Foris, 1981.
- [5] N. Chomsky, *The Minimalist Program*, Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 1995.
- [6] N. Chomsky, "Minimalist inquiries," in *Step by Step. Essays on Minimalist Syntax in Honor of Howard Lasnik*, R. Martin, D. Michaels and J. Uriagereka, Eds. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2000, pp. 89-155.
- [7] N. Chomsky, "Derivation by phase", in *Ken Hale: A Life in Language*, M. Kenstowicz, Ed. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2001.
- [8] R. Cooper, "The interpretation of pronouns," in *Syntax and Semantics*, F. Henry and H. Schnelle, Eds. New York: Academic Press, 1979, pp. 61-92.
- [9] A. M. Di Sciullo, "Morphological phases," in *Proceedings of the 4th GLOW in Asia 2003, Generative Grammar in a Broader Perspective. The Korean Generative Grammar Circle*, H.-J. Yoon, Ed. 2003, pp. 113-136.
- [10] A. M. Di Sciullo, "Morphological relations in asymmetry theory," in *Asymmetry in Grammar, volume 2: Morphology, Phonology and*

- Acquisition* A.M. Di Sciullo, Ed. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 2003, pp. 11-38.
- [11] A.M. Di Sciullo, "Domains of argument structure asymmetries," in *Proceedings of the 7th Multiconference on Systemics, Cybernetics, and Informatics (SCI 2005)*, N. Callaos, W. Lesso, K. Horimoto, Eds. Orlando, Florida, pp. 316-320, 2005.
- [12] A. M. Di Sciullo, *Asymmetry in Morphology*. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2005.
- [13] A. M. Di Sciullo, "Asymmetry theory in internet infrastructure," in *International Journal of Electronic Business*, Vol 3: Special Issue on: Multidisciplinary, Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research in Electronic Business, pp. 228-238, 2005.
- [14] A. M. Di Sciullo and C. Aguero, "Natural language asymmetries and the construction of question answering systems," in *Proceedings of the 7th Multiconference on Systemics, Cybernetics, and Informatics (SCI 2003)*, vol. 1.1, *Information Systems. Technologies and Applications*. N. Callaos, A.M. Di Sciullo, T. Ohta and T.K. Liu, Eds. Orlando, Florida, pp.13-18, 2003.
- [15] G. Evans, "Pronouns," *Linguistic Inquiry* vol. 11, pp. 337-362. 1980.
- [16] D. Fox, *Economy and Scope Interpretation*. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2000.
- [17] J. Groenendijk and M. Stokhof, "Dynamic Montague Grammar," in *Papers from the Second Symposium on Logic and Language*, L. Kálmán and L. Pólos, Eds. Budapest: Akadémiai Kiadó, pp. 3-48, 1990.
- [18] J. Groenendijk and M. Stokhof, "Dynamic predicate logic," *Linguistics and Philosophy*, vol. 14, pp. 39-100, 1990.
- [19] K. Hale and J. Keyser, *Prolegomena to a Theory of Argument Structure*. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2002.
- [20] H. Heim, *The semantics of definite and indefinite NPs*. University of Massachusetts, Amherst Ph.D. dissertation. 1982.
- [21] J. Hobbs, "Resolving pronouns reference", *Lingua* 44, pp. 339-352, 1987.
- [22] R. Kayne, *The Antisymmetry of Syntax*, Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 1994.
- [23] H. Kemp, "A theory of truth and semantic representation," in *Formal Methods in the Study of Language*. J. Groenendijk, J. Janssen, and M. Stokhof, Eds. Mathematical Center, Amsterdam, 1981.
- [24] C. Kennedy and B. Boguraev, "Anaphora for everyone: pronominal anaphora resolution without a parser", *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING'96)*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 1996, pp. 113-118.
- [25] S. Lappin and H. Leass, "An algorithm for pronominal anaphora resolution". *Computational Linguistics*, vol. 4, pp. 535-561, 1994.
- [26] R. May, *Logical Form: Its Structure and Interpretation*. Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 1985.
- [27] R. Mitkov, *Anaphora Resolution*, Edinburgh, London, Pearson Education, 2002.
- [28] A. Moro, *Dynamic Antisymmetry*, Cambridge, Mass.: The MIT Press, 2000.
- [29] E. Raimy, "Asymmetry and linearization in phonology," in *Asymmetry in Grammar. Volume 2: Morphology, Phonology and Acquisition*. A. M. Di Sciullo, Ed. Amsterdam/ Philadelphia: John Benjamins, pp. 129-146, 2003.
- [30] C. Roberts, "Modal subordination and pronominal anaphora in discourse," *Linguistic and Philosophy*, vol. 12, pp. 683-721, 1986.
- [31] J. Uriagereka, "Multiple spell-out," in *Working Minimalism*, S. D. Epstein and M. Hornstein, Eds. Cambridge, Mass.: MIT Press, pp. 251-283, 1999.
- [32] R. Wall, *Introduction to Mathematical Linguistics*, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1972.